

A GENERAL COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR DESIGNING MORPHING STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Morphing structures have, for many years, held the promise as the next enabler of weight reductions for the aerospace industry. The premise behind this idea is simple – if structures can be designed to adapt their shape to more optimally conform to different loading conditions, then structural efficiency is improved as a result. In fact, this multifunctionality has a very strong empirical proponent: Nature. Birds, for example, can adapt the camber and angle of attack of their wings to different flight scenarios. Even though some of the concepts found in nature are already being exploited in aircraft structures, such as slats and flaps, they often rely on rigid load-bearing components connected to heavy hydraulic or electric actuators.

Composite materials play a fundamental role in enabling morphing structures, because their orthotropy can be exploited to design structures with high stiffness in one direction, say the loading direction, and low stiffness in another direction, a potential actuating direction. Hence, composites create the opportunity for elastic tailoring. Furthermore, the laminated nature of advanced composites facilitates a union of materials with dissimilar thermal expansion coefficients, which can be used to build devices that exhibit large-scale shape changes in response to variations in the surrounding temperature [1]. Finally, the geometric nonlinearity of thin-walled shells can be conveniently coupled with the orthotropy of composite materials to design bi- or even tri-stable shells [2].

To date, the adoption of morphing structures has been hampered by two open research questions:

1. How to design structures and use materials that are sufficiently stiff to reliably carry the operational loads, while simultaneously providing sufficient flexibility for actuation?

2. How to analyse these structures accurately and efficiently, and particularly in a manner that is compatible with accepted methods used in industry?

The second question is especially poignant as confidence in computational tools can serve as an enabler for non-conventional designs. To date, there is no unique way of designing morphing structures. In recent years, a particular focus has been on specialised analytical and computational techniques tailored for the analysis of morphing structures [1-7], usually based on the classical *von Kármán* strains (small strains, small displacements and moderate rotations). However, an agreed “best” method has not yet been established. A major drawback of these specialised approaches is that they are often restricted to simple geometries and cannot readily be integrated with the standard tools used in industry, such as the finite element method.

In some cases, commercial finite element packages are used to analyse morphing structures. Most of the time, these analyses are rather *ad hoc*, because structural instabilities that are exploited to design multi-stable structures cannot be treated robustly. Rather, the engineer needs to be aware of possible instabilities and distinct stable configurations *a priori*, and then “coax” the algorithm to land on the required mode shape, using, for example, initial imperfections. Such an approach is ill-suited and computationally prohibitive for preliminary design exploration or parametric studies, and especially not scalable for industrial use. Thus, a more robust modelling framework is needed.

2 Generalised path-following

The ideal computational framework for morphing structures includes, but is not limited to, the following characteristics:

1. Applicable to arbitrary (thin-walled) geometries.
2. Applicable to large displacements and rotations (e.g. total Lagrangian framework) such that a large variety of structural instabilities is accounted for.
3. Be able to detect critical instability points and allow branch switching onto secondary paths without recourse to initial imperfections.
4. Allow rapid parametric studies of critical points with respect to any geometric or constitutive parameter.
5. Readily integrated with accepted computational methods used in industry.

One possible framework that addresses all of these points is the so-called *generalized path-following technique*. With the advent of catastrophe theory, the notion of the equilibrium surface [8], whose shape can be used to identify the stability of the underlying structure with respect to changes in governing parameters, was introduced to the structural mechanics community. However, a robust computational framework was not introduced until the seminal papers by Rheinboldt in the 1980's. These concepts allowed, for example, loci of bifurcation and/or limit points to be traced directly with respect to any parameter and switching between different equilibrium paths. Starting from the mid 1990's, Eriksson and co-workers [10] established themselves as the main proponents and developers of generalised path-following, presenting numerous examples where the approach proved to be of great benefit, while also providing details on how the technique could be incorporated into commercial nonlinear finite element codes. More recently the technique has been successfully applied to the analysis of bi-stable plates and shells for morphing structures [6].

A generalized path-following algorithm couples a numerical continuation solver, capable of detecting critical instability points, switching to secondary bifurcated branches and evaluating the parametric response of critical points with respect to any other variable, with the versatility of the finite element method. Hence, the term *generalized path-following* refers to the fact that any arbitrary curve, e.g. fundamental path, bifurcated path, locus of critical points, etc., on a non-linear equilibrium surface can be traced using an arc-length solver.

As an example, consider the classic snap-through equilibrium path of a centrally loaded arch with supported ends as shown in Figure 1. A symmetry-breaking bifurcation point exists before the maximum point, such that the arch will bifurcate onto this secondary path on its way to the inverted configuration. As shown in Figure 1, the generalised path-following algorithm detects the location of all critical points exactly (to within predefined numerical precision) and then branches onto the bifurcated path to provide a complete picture of the nonlinear behaviour.

Figure 1. Snap-through of a centrally loaded cylindrical arch under displacement control. The generalised path-following algorithm computes the bifurcation points while solving the fundamental path, and then readily continues onto the symmetry-breaking bifurcation path that characterises the snap through. All red points are statically unstable whereas all blue points statically stable.

3 A model problem

The aim of the present work is therefore to showcase the capabilities of generalized path-following by means of a classical example problem from the literature (see e.g. [1]) – a [0/90] cross-ply laminate that, upon a change in temperature, morphs from one cylindrical configuration to an orthogonal cylindrical configuration via twisting (see Figure 2). This twisted mode shape corresponds to a bifurcation path that emanates from the fundamental equilibrium path. Therefore, this path can only be

captured reliably in commercial finite element codes with the use of initial imperfections and consequently, this type of analysis *depends on* initial knowledge of the existence of this state. Within the generalised path-following framework such preliminary knowledge is not required because the algorithm automatically detects critical points and transitions onto possible bifurcation paths. Furthermore, the sensitivity of bifurcation points with respect to changing geometric parameters is readily investigated.

Figure 2. A thermally activated morphing [0/90] cross-ply laminate transitioning from one stable cylindrical shape to another via an intermediate twisting mode [1].

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